

Online database of published wideband acoustic immittance (WAI) measurements

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Abstract. The only public-facing database of published WAI measurements has been designed, constructed, and deployed. The database has evolved over the past nine years and now includes ears of all ages, both normal and abnormal ears, and ear canals in both ambient and pressurized conditions. The database is implemented in MySQL, is hosted on a server at Smith College, and can be accessed via a corresponding website (doi.org/10.35482/egr.001.2022). Anyone can access the database and researchers are encouraged to submit published data for inclusion in the database; the website includes directions to submit and download data, code books for all data columns, and a Shiny Web Application to allow for real-time dynamic exploration of the data. The database contains nearly 5 million rows of WAI data from 43 publications that total 12,644 ears with labelled hearing status from 8,697 unique subjects. About 91% of these data come from normal-hearing ears with the remaining 9% coming primarily from ears with middle-ear fluid but also from ears with a range of abnormalities including 128 ears with stapes fixation. Details about the content and structure of the database and a certification process that confirms that all database rows match their respective publication will be described. Researchers can utilize the database for many reasons, including complementing the new NIH data sharing requirements, comparing new data to previously published data, comparing WAI measurements across different measurement equipment and ear conditions, and downloading data to inform future modeling and machine-learning efforts.

INTRODUCTION

Wideband acoustic immittance (WAI) measures (e.g., absorbance, impedance) provide an objective, noninvasive diagnostic tool for some middle-ear pathologies and can be measured clinically using one of three FDA-approved devices [1, 2, 3]. At the same time, there are relatively large variations in WAI measures among normal ears (e.g., Rosowski et. al (2012) [4]), and diagnostic criteria for abnormal ears are still lacking even though many publications have shown systematic differences between normal and some abnormal ears (e.g., Nakajima et. al (2013) [5]).

Most WAI publications are limited by relatively small datasets that compare a group of normal subjects to a group of subjects with one or more specific pathological conditions. Often such datasets are shared in an ad hoc manner among researchers with relevant parameters not always controlled (e.g., measurement equipment, age, measurement technique, sex, race). The WAI database described here provides a mechanism to share published data among all researchers and to also control for and understand differences in measurement parameters. Ultimately, the ability for multiple researchers to pool their data allows for larger numbers of measurements and extended analyses related to the development of WAI measures for clinical application. As a specific example, this database also supports the need for substantially more WAI measurements for the application of machine learning techniques to interpret WAI measurements.

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DATABASE STRUCTURE AND VERIFICATION

The WAI database has been designed and implemented in MySQL and sits on a server hosted at Smith College. The database can be accessed via its corresponding website at <http://www.science.smith.edu/wai-database/>. Some important details about the database include: (1) Anyone can access the database online, and any researcher can request to have their peer-reviewed de-identified published data included in the database; (2) The website includes a Shiny Web Application to allow for real-time dynamic exploration of the data; and (3) Rules for data inclusion and standards for data coding are included on the website.

The database includes three tables: “PI_Info”, “Subjects”, and “Measurements”. Figure 1 summarizes the fields and corresponding descriptions, variable types, and primary keys for each table. The format of the database is primarily stable, but as published data are added, categorical values are added as needed; for example, different pathological conditions associated with experimental design require additions to the possible values for “EarStatus”. When a quantity is not known, it is entered as “NULL.” In addition to absorbance, when available, both magnitude and phase data of the impedance are included within measurements, allowing for the calculation of any WAI quantity.

We work with authors to format their data to the structure of the WAI database. Before uploading data to the database, we apply a certification process to confirm that data within the database match their publication. Relevant figures within the publication are identified, digitized from .jpg images, and ultimately the original figures are compared directly to the data formatted for the database to demonstrate that they match; in cases where differences occur we work with the authors to fix mistakes and ensure that the database data is consistent with their published data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 summarizes the 43 publications in the database as of May 2024, which collectively include nearly 5 million rows of WAI data that total 12,644 ears with labelled hearing status from 8,697 unique subjects. About 91% of these data come from normal-hearing ears with the remaining 9% coming primarily from ears with middle-ear fluid but also from ears with a range of abnormalities including 128 ears with stapes fixation. We continue to work with authors of additional publications to include their data and have identified 10 publications for which the authors report that individual data are no longer available. This unavailability of data demonstrates another need for the WAI database; as researchers move institutions or retire it can become difficult to access historical data that remain useful. Additionally, the database development and corresponding analyses have highlighted the need for researchers to report subject information that is more-often-than-not unavailable with the published data or historical subject records, including: subject age, sex, race, and ethnicity.

Figure 3 plots the mean absorbances from each of the 19 publications within the WAI database that include normal-hearing adult ears. Here the studies are color-coded as cool (blue/purple) colors when the Titan instrument was used, warm (red/yellow) colors when the HearID instrument was used, and gray scale colors for other noncommercial instruments. The two low-frequency outlier datasets in gray [6, 7] were both measured using a noncommercial system that uses the surge impedance to estimate the cross-sectional area of the canal for the absorbance calculation instead of the Titan and HearID systems’ methodology of using an assumed constant area. In addition to this one example of absorbance means among normal-hearing adult ears, the WAI database enables numerous other comparisons, for example, between specific age ranges that include babies and children, or comparisons across different ear status or impedance measures or any other parameters coded within the database (e.g., Fig. 1). Because all individual measurements are also in the database, statistical analyses can also be applied across datasets.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

New and additional WAI measurements will benefit the established database, allowing us and other researchers to utilize the full range of subject populations and ear conditions that are central to defining standards and methods to use WAI measurements as a noninvasive and objective measure of middle-ear status. Continued prospective database collecting supports the NIH data sharing requirements and incorporates non-NIH funded research. Fig. 2 demonstrates that there is still great need for additional WAI measurements, especially on adult ears with middle-ear pathologies (all types) and measurements that include WAI measures beyond only absorbance (e.g., impedance magnitudes and angles).

Column Number	Table (3 Unique)	Field (Column)	Description / Domain Values (categorical values bolded)	Variable Type	Primary Key
1	PI_Info	Identifier	Last name of the first author and publication year (e.g., Voss_2014) [Same field in PI_Info, Subjects and Measurements tables]	VARCHAR	1 of 1
2	PI_Info	Year	Publication year	INT	no
3	PI_Info	Authors	Publication authors	TEXT	no
4	PI_Info	AuthorsShortList	Publication authors abbreviated (upto 2 authors or et al.)	TEXT	no
5	PI_Info	Title	Publication title	TEXT	no
6	PI_Info	Journal	Publication journal (abbreviated with accepted form)	TEXT	no
7	PI_Info	URL	Publication URL	TEXT	no
8	PI_Info	Abstract	Published abstract in text format	TEXT	no
9	PI_Info	DataSubmitterName	Name of person who submitted data	TEXT	no
10	PI_Info	DataSubmitterEmail	Email for person who submitted data	TEXT	no
11	PI_Info	DateSubmitted	Date the data were submitted to this database (mm/dd/yyyy)	TEXT	no
12	PI_Info	PI_Notes	Relevant information regarding the data.	TEXT	no
1	Subjects	Identifier	Last name of the first author and publication year (e.g., Voss_2014) [Same field in PI_Info, Subjects and Measurements tables]	VARCHAR	1 of 2
2	Subjects	SubjectNumber	Assigned by the PI unless otherwise noted [Same field in Subjects and Measurements]	INT	1 of 2
3	Subjects	SessionTotal	Total number of sessions measured on subject. Differentiates multiple measurements on a subject by session. One session can include measurements on both the left and right ear or just one or the other ear. A session can also include measurements with multiple instruments.	INT	no
4	Subjects	AgeFirstMeasurement	Age of subject (in years) at their first measurement / first session. Null if not known.	FLOAT	no
5	Subjects	AgeCategoryFirstMeasurement	NICU (premature and measured during stay in NICU); Infant (not NICU and age birth through two years); Child (age two through 17 years); Adult (age 18 years and older); Unknown	VARCHAR	no
6	Subjects	Sex	Male; Female; Neither; Unknown	VARCHAR	no
7	Subjects	Race	Chinese (4 grandparents born in China); Asian (not Chinese); AfricanAmerican (4 grandparents born in USA and all identify as African American); Black; Caucasian; Mixed; Other; Unknown	VARCHAR	no
8	Subjects	Ethnicity	Hispanic; NonHispanic; Slavic; Arabian; Unknown	VARCHAR	no
9	Subjects	LeftEarStatusFirstMeasurement	Normal; AssumedNormal; Abnormal; Unknown	VARCHAR	no
10	Subjects	RightEarStatusFirstMeasurement	Normal; AssumedNormal; Abnormal; Unknown	VARCHAR	no
11	Subjects	SubjectNotes	Information regarding the subject and their measurements	TEXT	no
1	Measurements	Identifier	Last name of the first author and publication year (e.g., Voss_2014) [Same field in PI_Info, Subjects and Measurements tables]	VARCHAR	1 of 8
2	Measurements	SubjectNumber	Assigned by the PI unless otherwise noted [Same field in Subjects and Measurements]	INT	1 of 8
3	Measurements	Session	Session=1 for first measurement per ear per instrument. Differentiate multiple measurements by session. One session can include measurements on both the left and right ear or just one or the other ear or measurements with multiple instruments.	INT	1 of 8
4	Measurements	Ear	Right; Left; Unknown	VARCHAR	1 of 8
5	Measurements	Instrument	HearID; Titan; preHearID; preTitan; Other	VARCHAR	1 of 8
6	Measurements	Age	Age at measurement in years. NULL if not known	FLOAT	no
7	Measurements	AgeCategory	NICU (premature and measured during stay in NICU); Infant (not NICU and age birth through two years); Child (age two through 17 years); Adult (age 18 years and older); Unknown	VARCHAR	no
8	Measurements	EarStatus	Normal; Multiple; Other; Unknown; Unknown Abnormal; Conductive Nonspecific; Conductive Assumed; Fixation; Disarticulation; SCD; SCD Repaired; Fluid Assumed; Fluid Confirmed; OM Empty; OM Partial; OM Full; Pressure Negative; Pressure Positive; SNHL; SNHL severe; SNHL mild; Tube Patent; Post Surgical; Occlusion000; Occlusion010; Occlusion020; Occlusion030; Occlusion040; Occlusion050; Occlusion060; Occlusion070; Occlusion080; Occlusion090; Occlusion100	VARCHAR	no
9	Measurements	TPP	Middle ear pressure via tympanometric peak pressure (daPa). If unknown, NULL. Note, tympanometric TPP at 226 Hz may differ from TPP measured via Titan-like instruments. Either may be reported here, depending on the study.	FLOAT	no
10	Measurements	AreaCanal	Ear-canal area in m ² used to calculate absorbance. NULL if not known.	FLOAT	no
11	Measurements	PressureCanal	Static pressure held in ear canal with pressurized sweep (da Pa). When ambient, set to 0	FLOAT	1 of 8
12	Measurements	SweepDirection	Downswept (pressured canal swept from positive to negative pressure); Upswept (pressured canal swept from negative to positive pressure); Ambient (not applicable, ambient only measurements); Unknown (pressurized canal but sweep direction unknown);	VARCHAR	1 of 8
13	Measurements	Frequency	Frequency (Hz)	FLOAT	1 of 8
14	Measurements	Absorbance	Absorbance at probe location (equal to 1 minus power reflectance)	FLOAT	no
15	Measurements	Zmag	Impedance magnitude at probe location. MKS units. NULL if not available	FLOAT	no
16	Measurements	Zang	Impedance angle at probe location. Units of cycles. NULL if not available	FLOAT	no

FIGURE 1. Publications within the WAI database summarized by number of unique ears with labeled hearing status

Publication		# Normal Ears			# Abnormal Ears		
		Adult	Child	Baby	Adult	Child	Baby
1	Abur et al. (2014)	14	0	0	0	0	0
2	Aithal et al. (2013)	0	0	66	0	0	0
3	Aithal et al. (2014)	0	0	148	0	0	0
4	Aithal et al. (2014b)	0	0	208	0	0	95
5	Aithal et al. (2015)	0	0	183	0	0	8
6	Aithal et al. (2017a)	0	0	325	0	0	0
7	Aithal et al. (2017b)	0	0	78	0	0	0
8	Aithal et al. (2019a)	6	96	0	11	32	0
9	Aithal et al. (2019b)	0	36	0	0	85	0
10	Aithal et al. (2020a)	0	59	0	0	60	0
11	Aithal et al. (2020b)	25	24	0	43	23	0
12	Aithal et al. (2022)	0	0	249	0	0	0
13	AlMakadma et al. (2021)	0	0	77	0	0	0
14	Downing et al. (2022)	0	924	0	0	0	0
15	Ellison et al. (2012)	0	17	42	0	10	43
16	Feeney et al. (2017)	57	0	0	0	0	0
17	Groon et al. (2015)	21	0	0	0	0	0
18	Hunter et al. (2016)	0	0	132	0	0	0
19	Keefe et al. (2003) *	0	0	0	0	0	0
20	Keefe et al. (2012)	0	43	0	0	35	0
21	Keefe et al. (2017)	23	0	0	25	0	0
22	Lewis et al. (2015)	14	0	0	0	0	0
23	Lewis (2018)	30	0	0	0	0	0
24	Liu et al. (2008)	92	0	0	0	0	0
25	Merchant et al. (2010)	0	0	30	0	0	0
26	Merchant et al. (2015)	0	0	0	40	0	0
27	Merchant et al. (2020)	5	5	0	7	20	0
28	Merchant et al. (2021)	0	7	7	0	16	13
29	Myers et al. (2018)	0	0	796	0	0	263
30	Nakajima et al. (2012)	0	0	0	31	0	0
31	Pitaro et al. (2016)	0	0	156	0	0	69
32	Rosowski et al. (2012)	58	0	0	0	0	0
33	Sanford et al. (2009)	0	0	375	0	0	80
34	Sanford et al. (2014)	0	0	0	0	23	21
35	Shahnaz et al. (2006)	237	0	0	0	0	0
36	Shaver and Sun (2013)	48	0	0	0	0	0
37	Śliwa et al. (2020)**	133	0	0	102	0	0
38	Sun et al. (2016)	84	0	0	0	0	0
39	Sun et al. (2023)	3,309	2,281	0	0	0	0
40	Voss and Allen (1994)	10	0	0	0	0	0
41	Voss et al. (2010)	12	0	0	0	0	0
42	Voss et al. (2016)	0	0	22	0	0	15
43	Werner et al. (2010)	267	0	643	0	0	0
TOTAL		4,445	3,492	3,537	259	304	607
TOTAL (A, Z , _Z)		655	29	1,773	78	46	403

* Keefe et al. (2000) Data in database for 1405 infant subjects, but ears are not labelled)

** Śliwa et al. (2020) More ears in database than publication (133 vs 126 for Normal and 102 vs 90 for Fixation)

FIGURE 2. Publications within the WAI database summarized by number of unique ears with labeled hearing status [4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46]. Total indicates number of ears with Absorbance measurements, and Total (A, |Z|, /Z) indicates number of ears with all three WAI measures (publications in bold italics). Hearing statuses for 1405 baby subjects in Keefe et al. (2003) are pending.

FIGURE 3. Mean absorbance from normal-hearing adult ears from each of the 19 studies within the WAI database that includes this demographic (as of May 15, 2024). Noted in the legend are the peer-reviewed publications associated with the datasets, the number of individual ears, and the instrument category used in the study. When multiple measurements were made on the same ear, the average from those measurements was used in the calculation across subjects for a given study. Some subjects have measurements on both right and left ears, and some subjects have measurements from only one ear; this figure includes every ear in the database and does not control for the effect of number of ears from each subject. All measurements here were made at ambient ear-canal static pressure except for Śliwa et al. (2020), as they only published absorbance measurements with the canal pressure set as close as possible to the tympanic peak pressure in the Titan’s “downswept” mode.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

Merchant, Gabrielle: Are there any known limitations to submitting data (or barriers) that might be why not all investigators with published WAI data have submitted? *Response: The biggest issue seems to be that some data are lost when researchers move institutions, retire, or the data are simply older. Additionally, it can be time consuming for researchers to locate their data and share it with us.*